

Contributions of Demographic Features, Medications, and Illicit Drugs to Opioid Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse

Sean M. Shiverick
Indiana University-Bloomington
smshiver@iu.edu

ABSTRACT

The misuse and abuse of prescription opioids (MUPO) is influenced by both personal and environmental factors. Aggregated measures of pain reliever use, misuse, and abuse, demographic factors, use of medications, and illicit drugs, were constructed using data from the National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH 2015-2016). Weighted Least Squares (WLS) regression of pain reliever misuse and abuse (PRLMISAB) was conducted with a subset of $N = 6,946$ individuals who self-reported MUPO. Age, sex, marital status, and education level were negatively related to PRLMISAB, whereas use of medications and illicit drugs were positively associated with PRLMISAB. Individuals who were older, female, married, with more education were less likely to misuse and abuse opioid pain relievers than their counterparts. The effects of these demographic factors varied by age group. Use of any opioid pain relievers predicted PRLMISAB across all age groups, followed by tranquilizer use. Overall, the proportion of PRLMISAB was higher among individuals who had used heroin than those who had not; however, cocaine and amphetamines were more influential predictors of PRLMISAB than heroin. The relation between illicit drug use and PRLMISAB also varied by age group. Heroin predicted PRLMISAB between 18 to 49 years; use of amphetamines significantly predicted PRLMISAB between 12 to 35 years. Some demographic features may play a role in helping to prevent or decrease opioid misuse, and contribute to resilience in overcoming opioid abuse and addiction.¹

KEYWORDS

Modeling, Opioid Misuse, Pain Reliever Abuse, Linear Regression

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, prescription opioid misuse, abuse, and addiction in the U.S. has become a major crisis with serious public health consequences. In 2015, an estimated 2 million Americans suffered from substance use disorders related to opioid pain medications such as oxycodone and hydrocodone [3, 10]. Of patients legitimately prescribed opioids for chronic pain, approximately 25% misused them, between 8% to 12% became addicted, and 4% to 6% transitioned to heroin [2, 17]. Opioid dependence and addiction are chronic health conditions; following treatment, many addicted individuals are at high risk for relapse and overdose death [14]. Since 1999, the number of overdose deaths from prescription opioids has more than quadrupled [8]. The economic cost of the opioid crisis since 2001 is estimated to exceed one trillion dollars [5].

Previous studies have identified several risk factors for opioid abuse, including, but not limited to: gender, ethnicity, comorbid psychological disorders, and non-opioid drug abuse [6, 18, 19]. Rates of hospitalization for prescription opiate overdose (POD) are higher for females than males, and the increase in POD is highest for Whites compared to Blacks or Hispanics [16]. Supply-based interventions to reduce the availability of prescription opioids have produced a shift to heroin use, and the exponential increase in POD and heroin overdose deaths (HOD) are correlated [7, 12]. The current study examined the contributions of demographic features, use of medications, and illicit drugs as predictors of pain reliever misuse and abuse. It was hypothesized that personal characteristics may play a role in resisting or overcoming opioid dependence and addiction. According to this view, some individuals may be more resilient than others in recovering from opioid abuse and addiction. Insofar as the non-medical use of prescription opioids also varies by age [13], models of pain reliever misuse and abuse were compared across age groups.

1.1 Modeling Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse

Many researchers have analyzed the probability that an individual abused or misused opioids (or did not) with logistic regression [6, 7, 13, 16, 19]. The logistic model takes a binary variable as the outcome, with the following form: $Pr(abuse = 1) = F(\alpha + \sum_j(\beta_j * X_{ij}))$. The function $F(z)$ is a cumulative logistic distribution. X_{ij} represents a matrix of observation-related independent variables, α and β_j are the parameters to be estimated in the model. In the present study, pain reliever misuse and abuse was assessed along a continuum by aggregating responses for several related binary measures into a single variable. Similarly, binary responses for related independent measures were summed, creating several aggregated variables as predictors in a linear regression model, rather than a logit model. The general linear model (Ordinary Least Squares) estimates the coefficients of the independent variables in relation to the dependent variable, with some degree of error, in the following form:

$$Y_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_i X_{ij} + u_i \quad (1)$$

The classical linear regression model is based on several assumptions, including: (a) the model is linear in the parameters, (b) the fixed x-values are independent of the error term, (c) the mean value of the error terms is zero, (d) constant variance of error terms (i.e., *homoscedasticity*) (e) non-collinearity among the independent variables, (f) independent observations (i.e., non-autocorrelation), and (g) the x-values are not all the same [4]. An important assumption for the present study is that the disturbances u_i all have the same variances. Heteroscedastic (i.e., *non-equal*) variances is a common occurrence in socioeconomic variables measured in cross-section, but can also arise due to skewness in the distribution of one or

¹ Sean Shiverick is with the School of Informatics and Computing. This project was completed in partial fulfillment of requirements for the Master's in Data Science program at IU-Bloomington in May, 2018. Address for correspondence: smshiver@iu.edu

Table 1: Summary of Variables in the NSDUH 2015-16 Aggregated Data Set

<i>Dependent Variable</i>	Label
Prescription Opioid Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse (0-12 Scale)	PRLMISAB
<i>Demographic Variables</i>	
Age Category (1=12-17 years, 2=18-25, 3=26-34, 4=35-49, 5=50 and older)	AGECAT
Biological Sex (0=Male, 1=Female)	SEX
Marital Status (0=Unmarried, 1=Divorced, 2=Widowed, 3=Married)	MARRIED
Education (1=H.S. or Less, 2=H.S. Grad., 3=Some College, 4=College Grad.)	EDUCAT
Size of City/Metropolitan Region (1=Rural, 2=Small, 3=Large)	CTYMETRO
Health Problems Aggregated (0-10 scale)	HEALTH
Mental Health, Aggregated: adult depression, emotional distress (0-10 scale)	MENTHLTH
Treatment for Drugs and Alcohol in past year, Aggregated (0-5 scale)	TRTMNT
Mental Health Treatment, Aggregated (Likert scale, 1-10)	MHTRTMT
<i>Medication and Drug Use Variables</i>	
Any Prescribed Opioid Pain Reliever Use in past year, Aggregated (1-10 scale)	PRLANY
Tranquilizer use, past year, Aggregated (Likert scale, 0-5)	TRQLZRS
Sedative use, past year, Aggregated (0-5 scale)	SEDATVS
Heroin use, past year, Aggregated (0-5 scale)	HEROINUSE
Cocaine and Crack Cocaine Use in past year, Aggregated (0-5 scale)	COCAINE
Amphetamine and Methamphetamine Use in past year, Aggregated (0-5 scale)	AMPHETMN
Hallucinogen Use in past year, Aggregated (0-5 scale)	HALUCNG

more regressors in the model, or from incorrect functional form (e.g., linear versus log-linear models). Outliers can also contribute to heteroscedasticity. If the assumption of homoscedasticity is not met, the ordinary least squares (OLS) parameter estimates are no longer “best”, are not efficient as they do not provide the minimum variance, and produce unreliable statistics.

In the presence of heteroscedasticity, Weighted Least Squares (WLS)—a subset of Generalized Least Squares (GLS)—provides estimates with a smaller variance to replace the OLS estimators. To control for heteroscedasticity using WLS, first the primary contributing variable(s) must be identified; then an appropriate transformation is carried out on the data to correct for heteroscedasticity. OLS is then applied to the transformed data. WLS provides estimates which are *best, linear, unbiased* (i.e., “BLUE”). A common ad hoc assumption with WLS is that the error variance is proportional to the square of one of the explanatory variables: $\sigma^2 = (\sigma^2(X_{ij}^2))$ [4]. The original model is transformed by dividing through by the explanatory variable X_i . In the present study, it was assumed that Age primary variable contributing to heteroscedasticity, and WLS transformations were used to construct the model.

$$Y_i/X_2 = \beta_1/X_2 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 X_3/X_2 + \dots + \beta_i X_{ij}/X_2 + u_i/X_2 \quad (2)$$

1.2 National Survey on Drug Use and Health

Data for the study was derived from the National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH) from 2015 and 2016—obtained from the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Data Archive (SAMHDA) [1]. The NSDUH consists of over 2600 variables covering all aspects of substance use, misuse, dependency, abuse, and addiction for

tobacco, alcohol, medications and illicit drugs, including comprehensive demographic information, including health, mental health, substance treatment and counseling. According to the NSDUH codebook, sampling was weighted across states by population size for a representative distribution selected from 6,000 area segments. The sample design used five state sample size groups, drawing more heavily from the eight states with the largest population (e.g., CA, FL, IL, MI, NY, OH, PA, TX) which together account for 48 percent of the total U.S. population aged 12 or older. All identifying information in the public data set were collapsed (e.g., age categories) and state identifiers were removed from the public use file to ensure confidentiality. The NSDUH public-use files do not include geographic location, or demographic variables related to ethnicity or immigration status. For the purposes of the present study, approximately 90 variables from the NSDUH were selected and aggregated to construct a data set of 20 variables, 16 of which were used to construct the regression model (see Table 1).

1.3 Study Goals

The main goal of the study was to analyze the contributions of demographic features, medications, and illicit drugs as predictors of pain reliever misuse and abuse. It was hypothesized that demographic variables such as marital status and education level may play a preventive role in decreasing pain reliever misuse and abuse. As described above, past findings indicate that misuse of prescription opioids varies by age, and age group was considered as an important covariant in the model contributing to heteroscedasticity. WLS transformations were used to correct for heteroscedasticity due to age category. Pain reliever misuse and abuse was expected

Table 2: Summary Statistics for Aggregated Variables for Full Sample and Subset of Individuals Reporting Misuse and Abuse of Prescription Opioids (MUPO)

Variables	Full Sample (N = 25,432)				MUPO Subset (N = 6,946)		
	Mean	S.D.	Median	Range	Mean	S.D.	Median
PRL Misuse Abuse	1.74	3.30	0	12	6.38	3.11	7
Health Problems	2.77	1.15	3	7	2.71	1.11	3
Mental Health	1.57	2.37	0	12	2.21	2.71	1
Drug Treatment	0.15	0.89	0	10	0.43	1.48	0
MH Treatment	0.37	0.86	0	7	0.48	0.97	0
Any PRL Use	1.61	1.06	1	10	1.93	1.37	1
Tranquilizer Use	0.60	1.22	0	5	1.05	1.42	0
Sedative Use	0.12	0.50	0	5	0.18	0.62	0
Heroin Use	0.10	0.49	0	5	0.30	0.85	0
Cocaine use	0.38	0.80	0	5	0.83	1.10	0
Amphetamines	0.32	0.72	0	5	0.73	1.04	0
Hallucinogens	0.65	1.16	0	5	1.42	1.47	1

to decrease with age. It was predicted that use of non-opioid medications and illicit drugs would be related to increased pain reliever misuse and abuse. Specifically, heroin use was expected to be highly correlated with misuse and abuse of opioid pain relievers. Analyses were conducted using the full sample and the subset of individuals who reported ever misusing or abusing pain relievers. Finally, separate regression models were constructed for each age group to examine differences in the relative contribution of the predictor variables across different subsets for each age group.

2 METHOD

The following steps were included in the project workflow: (1) Data cleaning and preparation, (2) Exploratory data analysis, (3) Data Visualization, and (4) Construction of regression models for opioid pain reliever misuse and abuse.

2.1 Data Cleaning and Preparation

The data was extracted, cleaned and prepared using an interactive Python notebook [9]. NSDUH data files for 2015 and 2016 were downloaded from the SAMHDA website [1], and saved as data frame objects in Pandas. The initial data files consisted of 57,146 observations from 2015, and 56,897 observations for 2016, with over 2,600 features. The data was subset by columns, selecting approximately 90 variables that included demographic information, health, mental health, medication use, illicit drug use, and treatment for drugs or alcohol or mental health (a complete list of variables is described in a data codebook [15]). The following steps were taken to detect and remove inconsistencies in the data: (a) Remove missing values (i.e., *NaN*); (b) Recode blanks, non-responses, or legitimate skips (e.g., 99, 991, 993) to zero; (c) Recode dichotomous responses (0 = No, 1 = Yes); (d) Recode categorical variables to be consistent with amount or degree (1 = Low, 2 = Medium, 3 = High); (e) Rename selected variables for better description (e.g., DEPMELT = Major Depressive Episode Lifetime).

2.1.1 Aggregated Variables. Responses for related binomial variables were summed to create aggregated variables; Table 1 lists the

initial set of variables and range of scores. For example, a measure of overall health was created by combining any previous health problems (e.g., STDs, Hepatitis, HIV, Cancer, Hospitalization). Overall mental health was assessed as a combination of any adult major depressive episode, severe emotional distress, and suicidal thoughts, or plans. The use of any prescription opioid pain reliever medications taken in past year (PRLANY) was assessed by summing ten of the most commonly used opioids (e.g., Hydrocodone, Oxycodone, Tramadol, Morphine, Fentanyl, Oxymorphone, Demerol, Hydro-morphone). The main dependent variable, pain reliever misuse and abuse (PRLMISAB), was based on the self-reported non-medical use of prescription opioids not directed by a physician, use of pain relievers in amounts greater than prescribed, misuse of pain relievers in the past year or month, dependence or abuse of pain relievers, and use of pain relievers to “get high”. Similar aggregated measures were constructed for the use and misuse of prescription Tranquilizers, Sedatives, Heroin (HEROINUSE), Cocaine, Amphetamines, and Hallucinogens. Drug or alcohol treatment was summed across different treatment contexts (e.g., Inpatient, Outpatient, Hospital, MH Clinic, ER, Drug Treatment Status). Similarly, responses for mental health treatment or counseling were summed across different treatment settings.

2.1.2 Data Subsets. The data files were subset to select only respondents who indicated using any prescription opioid pain relievers; $n = 13,916$ individuals (24.35%) from 2015 and $n = 11,690$ individuals (20.54%) from 2016 were combined into a single file, providing a pooled, cross-sectional sample of $N=25,606$ observations. Preliminary examination of the data revealed 174 outliers that exceeded the range of the dependent variable and were excluded. The revised sample consisting of $N = 25,432$ observations (10,655 male, 14,777 female) with 17 variables was exported to CSV file. An additional data subset consisted of $N = 6,964$ individuals who reported misusing or abusing prescription opioids (i.e., MUPO).

Figure 1: Proportion of Individuals Reporting Opioid Pain Reliever Misuse or Abuse (PRLMISAB) by Age Group

3 RESULTS

3.1 Exploratory Data Analysis

Overall, 27.3% of the initial sample reported misusing or abusing prescription opioid pain relievers; however, the majority of individuals reported no pain reliever misuse or abuse. In general, pain reliever misuse and abuse was higher among younger age groups than older respondents. As shown in Figure 1, the proportion of pain reliever misuse or abuse was highest between 18 to 25 years, and decreased with age. More women (61%) than men (39%) reported using any prescription opioid medications, but equal proportions of men and women (50%) reported pain relievers misuse and abuse. Table 2 provides summary statistics of the aggregated variables measured on a scale for both the full sample and the MUPO subset. As seen in Table 2, the mean and standard deviation for the dependent variable are more robust in the MUPO subset than the full sample.

Figure 2: Proportion of Individuals Reporting Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse and Heroin Use (N=25,432)

Figure 2 shows the proportion of individuals who reported ever misusing prescription opioid pain relievers and/or ever using heroin.

The left side of Figure 2 shows that the majority of respondents (75%) had never misused opioid pain relievers or used heroin. As described above, approximately one-quarter of the initial sample reported misusing opioid pain relievers at some point. Although relatively few individuals reported ever using heroin (4.7% overall, 692 males, 505 females), the right side of Figure 2 shows that the proportion of individuals who had used heroin and misused pain relievers was more than three times greater than the proportion who reported using heroin not misusing opioid pain relievers. In addition, the proportion of pain reliever misuse and abuse for those who had ever used heroin was significantly greater than those than for those who had not, which is consistent with the hypothesis that the misuse of prescription opioids and heroin use are linked. (Note: some predictor variables used for exploratory analysis were excluded from the regression models presented in the following section: e.g., PRLMISEVR, HEROINEVR).

Figure 3: Plot of Residuals versus Predicted Values of the Dependent Variable: Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse (N = 25,432)

3.2 Linear Regression Models

3.2.1 Initial OLS Regression on the Full Sample. All regression models were constructed in SAS. First, pain reliever misuse and abuse was regressed on the 16 independent variables using OLS with the full sample; this regression was statistically significant, $F(16, 24947) = 520.47, p < 0.0001, (R^2 = 0.2504, \text{adjusted } R^2 = 0.2498)$. The variance inflation values and condition index were all within acceptable ranges, and the t-values for all but one regressor in the OLS model were significant, which indicated that near multicollinearity was not an issue in the data set. Examination of the residuals plotted against the predicted values of the dependent variable revealed an additional outlier that was removed (Figure 3). The White's test and Goldfield-Quandt test were both significant (see Technical Appendix), which indicated heteroscedasticity in the data; however, the plot of the residuals versus predicted values of the dependent variable, PRLMISAB in Figure 3, shows a bimodal trend in the variances that decreased over the predicted values. Some of the residual

Table 3: Weighted Least Squares (WLS) Parameter Estimates for Regression of Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse

Variables	Full Sample (N = 25,432)			MUPO Subset (N = 6,946)		
	Estimate	S.E.	t-value	Estimate	S.E.	t-Value
Intercept	1.656***	0.083	19.85	6.870***	0.154	44.72
Age Category	-0.370	0.028	-13.23	-0.312***	0.059	-5.31
Sex	-0.156***	0.039	-4.03	-0.154*	0.069	-2.24
Married	-0.041*	0.021	-2.02	-0.159***	0.039	-4.03
Education	-0.028	0.020	-1.41	-0.123***	0.037	-3.36
City/Metro Size	-0.016	0.025	-0.67	0.017	0.043	0.40
Health Problems	-0.021	0.019	-1.12	-0.041	0.034	-1.22
Mental Health	0.059***	0.011	5.22	-0.022	0.018	-1.25
Drug Treatment	0.190***	0.025	7.61	-0.13	0.024	-0.57
MH Treatment	-0.143***	0.033	-4.39	0.017	0.029	0.33
Any PRL Use	0.252***	0.020	12.62	0.290***	0.029	9.87
Tranquilizer Use	0.447***	0.021	21.40	0.116***	0.029	4.05
Sedative Use	0.192***	0.039	4.95	0.043	0.053	0.81
Heroin Use	0.358***	0.055	6.52	0.258***	0.059	4.36
Cocaine Use	0.350***	0.035	9.95	0.103*	0.043	2.38
Amphetamines	0.780***	0.030	25.93	0.232***	0.037	6.23
Hallucinogens	0.576***	0.023	25.66	0.006	0.030	0.21
Significance level:	*0.05,	**0.01	***0.001			

values were negative. As stated above, heteroscedasticity can occur due to skewness in one or more regressors in the model. The Durbin-Watson test was also significant, which indicated autocorrelation in the data, perhaps owing to model misspecification due to excluded variables.

3.2.2 Weighted Least Squares (WLS) Regression. To address heteroscedasticity, WLS transformations were applied to the data, based on the assumption that Age Category was primarily contributing to heteroscedasticity. The WLS regression was conducted using PROC MODEL in SAS, and yielded a statistically significant relationship between Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse and the independent variables, $F(16, 24947) = 542, p < 0.0001 (R^2 = 0.2437, \text{adjusted } R^2 = 0.2425)$. The WLS transformation reduced heteroscedasticity from the initial OLS model, but it was not completely eliminated from the data. The WLS parameter estimates for the full sample given on the left side of Table 3 show that Education Level, Size of City/Metropolitan area, and Health Problems were not significant predictors of pain reliever misuse and abuse. To focus on prescription opioid misuse and abuse, the next analysis used the subset of respondents who misused or abused prescription opioids (MUPO).

3.2.3 Regression Model for the MUPO Subset. The following regressions were conducted with the subset of $N = 6,478$ individuals who reported MUPO. The OLS regression on the MUPO subset was statistically significant, $F(16, 6461) = 51.69, p < 0.0001, (R^2 = 0.1135, \text{adjusted } R^2 = 0.1113)$. The White's test and Goldfield-Quandt tests were both statistically significant, which indicated heteroscedasticity in the MUPO subset. The WLS transformation was used to correct for heteroscedasticity due to Age Group. The WLS regression revealed a significant relationship between Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse and the independent variables, $F(16,$

Table 4: WLS Parameter Estimates for Final Model of Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse with MUPO Subset (N=6964)

Variable	Estimate	S.E.	t-Statistic
Intercept	6.850***	0.098	69.69
Age Category	-0.327***	0.058	-5.64
Sex	-0.170*	0.067	-4.02
Married	-0.158***	0.039	-4.02
Education	-0.130***	0.034	-3.81
Any PRL Use	0.289***	0.029	9.98
Tranquilizer Use	0.114***	0.028	4.14
Heroin Use	0.244***	0.057	4.24
Cocaine Use	0.102*	0.04	9.95
Amphetamines	0.231***	0.036	6.36
Significance level:	*0.05,	**0.01	***0.001

$6462) = 51.95, p < 0.0001 (R^2 = 0.1076, \text{adjusted } R^2 = 0.1056)$. The WLS parameter for the MUPO subset provided in the right side of Table 3 shows that the key demographic features were negatively related to pain reliever misuse and abuse, whereas medication use and use of illicit drugs was positively related to pain reliever misuse and abuse.

3.3 Final Model: WLS for the MUPO subset

The final model was obtained by excluding the non-significant independent variables from the previous WLS regression on the MUPO subset. The final WLS regression demonstrated a significant relationship between Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse and the independent variables, $F(16, 6462) = 51.95, p < 0.0001 (R^2 = 0.1071, \text{adjusted } R^2 = 0.0865)$. Overall, 10.71% of the variation in the

Table 5: Comparison of Final Regression Model by Age Category for MUPO Subset (with Standardized Estimates)

Variables	Age Group				
	12-17	18-25	26-35	36-49	50+
Intercept	6.156***	6.147***	5.774***	5.227***	5.859***
Sex	0.229 (0.045)	-0.474*** (-0.083)	-0.701*** (-0.115)	-0.019 (-0.003)	-0.433*** (-0.070)
Married	0.127 (0.022)	-0.300*** (-0.096)	-0.081 (-0.037)	-0.057 (-0.024)	-0.126 (-0.045)
Education	0	-0.065 (-0.020)	-0.120 (-0.037)	-0.159* (-0.049)	-0.352*** (-0.119)
Any PRL Use	0.184* (0.090)	0.390*** (0.171)	0.367*** (0.153)	0.435*** (0.169)	0.406*** (0.153)
Tranquilizer Use	0.010 (0.005)	0.159*** (0.080)	0.192** (0.085)	0.187** (0.080)	0.242** (0.097)
Heroin Use	0.183 (0.024)	0.196* (0.054)	0.314*** (0.098)	0.446** (0.103)	0.089 (0.018)
Cocaine Use	0.227 (0.064)	0.086 (0.032)	-0.073 (-0.026)	-0.045 (-0.015)	0.142 (0.048)
Amphetamines	0.306** (0.120)	0.170** (0.063)	0.201* (0.066)	0.143 (0.043)	-0.083 (-0.020)
<i>n</i>	685	2259	1506	1380	648
<i>Percent</i>	10.56	34.87	23.24	21.3	10
<i>F-test</i>	4.50***	30.52***	18.56***	15.17***	6.52***
<i>R-square</i>	0.0444	0.0979	0.0902	0.0813	0.0755
<i>Adj. R-square</i>	0.0346	0.0947	0.0845	0.076	0.0639
Significance level:	*0.05,	**0.01	***0.001		

predicted value of Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse in the MUPO subset was due to changes in the independent variables; and 8.65% of the variability in Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse was accounted for, taking into account the number of independent variables. The parameter estimates for the final WLS model are given in Table 4.

As seen in Table 4, demographic variables were negatively correlated with Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse (PRLMISAB): A one-unit change in Age Category yielded a -0.327 decrease in the predicted value of PRLMISAB, holding the effect of other independent variables constant. Similarly, there was a -0.17 decrease in PRLMISAB for females compared to males, all other factors considered equal. A one-unit change in Marital Status was associated with -0.158 decrease in PRLMA, holding constant other variables. And a one-unit increase in Educational Level was associated with -0.130 decrease in PRLMA, with other predictors held constant.

Use of prescription medications and illicit drugs was positively correlated with Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse in the MUPO subset. A one-unit increase in Any Pain Reliever Misuse or Abuse yielded a 0.289 unit increase in PRLMA, holding other variables constant. Likewise, a one-unit increase in Tranquilizer use was linked to a 0.114 unit increase in PRLMA. In terms of illicit drugs, a one-unit increase in Heroin use was associated with a 0.244 unit increase in PRLMA, as expected, holding constant the effects of other independent variables. A one-unit increase in Cocaine use was associated with a 0.102 increase in PRLMA. Finally, a one-unit

increase in Amphetamine use was related to a 0.231 unit increase in Pain Reliever Misuse and Abuse.

3.3.1 Final Regression Model by Age Category for MUPO Subset. Separate regressions were conducted for each age category using the set of predictors from the final model. Table 5 provides the OLS parameter estimates with standardized betas in parentheses, F-test, R^2 , adjusted R^2 , and significance level of the estimates. As shown in Table 5, the regression model F-test was significant for every age group; however, the significance of the parameter estimates for the regressors varied by age group. The standardized betas are given in parentheses as an indication of the relative contribution of each predictor.

In general, the influence of demographic features and illicit drugs varied considerably across age groups; In terms of demographic factors, Sex was a significant predictor of PRLMISAB between 18 to 36 years and over age 50, with the largest effect observed between 26 to 35 years. Marital status significantly predicted PRLMISAB only between the ages of 18-26, whereas education level significantly predicted PRLMISAB only for respondents age 36 years and older, with the largest effect at age 50 and older. As for illicit drugs, Heroin Use significantly predicted PRLMISAB between the ages of 18 to 49 years; with a larger effect between 26 to 49 years. Amphetamines significantly predicted PRLMISAB between 12 to 35 years, with the largest effect observed in the youngest age group. Surprisingly, Cocaine was not a significant predictor of PRLMISAB

at any age group, although it was a significant predictor when age was included as a regressor in the final model.

Of the medications and illicit drugs included in the final model with the MUPO subset, the use of any opioid pain relievers was the only predictor of PRLMISAB that was significant predicted across all age groups, and contributed the greatest amount in the change/effect in the dependent variable than any other regressor for the ages of 18 and above. For the youngest age group, between 12 to 17 years, Amphetamine use contributed more to change in PRLMISAB than Use of Any opioid Pain Relievers. Between 18 to 26 years, use of any opioid pain relievers contributed more than Marital Status, Sex, Tranquilizers, Amphetamines, or Heroin (in descending order). Between 26 to 35 years, any opioid pain reliever contributed more than Sex which contributed the second largest portion of change in the outcome, followed by Heroin, Tranquilizers, and Amphetamines. Between 36 to 49 years, use of any opioid pain relievers accounted for more change in the dependent variable than Heroin, Tranquilizers, and Education level. Finally, for respondents age 50 and up, any opioid pain reliever use contributed more than Education level, which accounted for the second largest amount of change in PRLMISAB, followed by Tranquilizers, and Sex, in decreasing order of contribution.

4 DISCUSSION

The results indicated that approximately one-quarter of individuals who had taken any prescribed opioid pain relievers reported misusing them, which replicates past findings. Pain reliever misuse and abuse varied by age, with the highest rates of misuse between 18 to 25 years, and decreased among older age groups. Demographic factors such as age, sex, marital status, and education level were associated with decreased pain reliever misuse and abuse, and the contribution of these demographic factors varied across age groups: Sex predicted PRLMISAB between 18 to 35 years, with the largest effect between the ages of 26 to 35. Marital status predicted PRLMISAB only between 18 to 25 years. Education level predicted PRLMISAB from age 36 and up, but had the largest contribution for the ages of 50 and older. As predicted, the use of medications and illicit drugs was related to increased misuse of pain relievers. Use of any opioid pain relievers predicted PRLMISAB across all ages, followed by Tranquilizer use, which predicted PRLMISAB for ages 18 and older. As predicted, misuse and abuse of pain relievers was associated with heroin use, as the proportion of pain reliever misuse and abuse was higher for individuals who had used heroin than those who had not. However, in the final model, with the MUPO subset, cocaine and amphetamines were more influential predictors of PRLMISAB than heroin. The effect of illicit drugs varied by age. Heroin predictor of PRLMISAB between the ages 18 to 36 years; however, Amphetamines contributed more to predicting PRLMISAB between 12 to 17 years, than any opioid pain reliever misuse. Although Cocaine predicted PRLMISAB when age was included in the final model, it was not a significant predictor for any of the regression models considered by age group separately. It is interesting to note that, in the final model, health, mental health, treatment, and counseling did not predict PRLMISAB, although these regressors were significant predictors in the initial regression model with the full sample.

4.1 Limitations

In selecting the best set of variables to model pain reliever misuse and abuse, the resulting tradeoff was a decrease in the proportion of variance accounted for (R^2) due to a reduction in sample size and number of independent variables in each successive model. The final regression model provided a parsimonious and interpretable model of opioid misuse and abuse, though it was based on a smaller sample, with a lower coefficient of determination. A limitation of the study is that misspecification may occur due to the exclusion of relevant variables such as socioeconomic status, ethnicity, or region from the model. In future, related proxy variables could be included to represent variance in the relationship of those missing variables with the dependent measure. Using aggregated variables may have masked the separate contributions of individual features. A drawback of assessing pain reliever misuse and abuse on a scale, taken as the sum of several binary responses, is that many aggregated variables had bimodal distributions that were highly skewed. It may have been appropriate to analyze the data using a logit model to obtain the log odds ratios of opioid pain reliever misuse and abuse. An initial goal of the study was to analyze trends in prescription opioid misuse over time using panel data. The sample used in this study included NSDUH for only two years, which may have limited the generalizability of the findings. In future, it would be preferable to combine NSDUH data across multiple years to construct a more complete data set, with an inclusive set of variables, to build more informative models of opioid misuse and abuse.

5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, demographic factors, medications, and illicit drugs contributed differently to the aggregated measure of prescription opioid misuse and abuse. The findings are consistent with the idea that personal characteristics may play a role in helping to prevent or decrease the misuse and abuse of opioids pain relievers. Overall, respondents who were older, female, married, with more education, were less likely to misuse and abuse opioid pain relievers than their counterparts. By contrast, any previous prescription opioid use, tranquilizer use, heroin, cocaine, or amphetamine use put people at increased risk for opioid misuse and abuse. The widespread availability and prescription of opioids for chronic pain is likely a primary contributing factor driving the rapid escalation of opioid addiction and abuse. On the other hand, the misuse and abuse of opioids may be influenced by risk factors that contribute to psychological and physical dependence. Theories of addiction suggest that situational cues or events can elicit a motivational state underlying relapse, as addictive behavior are reinstated by exposure to drugs, drug-related cues, or environmental stressors [14]. A lack of continuity in treatment also leaves many people in recovery at risk for relapse or possible overdose as they return to the same environments and social relationships associated with their drug use. The sharp increase in overdose deaths in the U.S. due to synthetic opioids (other than methadone) has coincided with the increased availability of illicit synthetic opioid, fentanyl [11]. Because the dosage levels and potency of illicit opioids are largely unknown, there is greater risk of drug overdose and death. This study may help raise awareness about personal characteristics that help individuals resist opioid misuse and dependency. Additional

research is needed to understand factors related to resilience in overcoming opioid abuse and addiction.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Portions of this paper were completed as part of a course project in Data Analysis and Modeling taught by Dr. Barry Rubin (SPEA Connect P507) at Indiana University in Spring 2018. The author would like to thank Professor Rubin and Dr. Venkat Nadella, the TA, for helpful guidance and feedback on the project proposal and analysis. Thanks to Taylor Roundtree for conducting tests and corrections for heteroscedasticity.

REFERENCES

- [1] Substance Abuse, Center for Behavioral Health Statistics Mental Health Services Administration, and Quality. 2016. *National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH) 2015*. Online data archive. United States Department of Health and Human Services., Ann Arbor, MI. <https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR50011.v1>
- [2] Robert G. Carlson, Ramzi W. Nahhas, Silvia S. Martins, and Raminta Daniulaityte. 2016. Predictors of transition to heroin use among initially non-opioid dependent illicit pharmaceutical opioid users: A natural history study. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence* 160 (2016), 127fi??134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2015.12.026>
- [3] Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2018. Opioid overdose: Understanding the epidemic. online. (Jan. 2018). <https://www.cdc.gov/drugoverdose/index.html>
- [4] Damodar N. Gujarati and Dawn C. Porter. 2009. *Basic Econometrics, 5th edition*. McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- [5] Altarum Institute. 2018. Economic Toll Of Opioid Crisis In U.S. Exceeded \$1 Trillion Since 2001. online. (Feb. 2018). <https://altarum.org/about/news-and-events/economic-toll-of-opioid-crisis-in-u-s-exceeded-1-trillion-since-2001> Ann Arbor, MI.
- [6] Rice JB, White AG, Birnbaum HG, Schiller M, Brown DA, and Roland CL. 2012. A Model to Identify Patients at Risk for Prescription Opioid Abuse, Dependence, and Misuse. *Pain Medicine* 13, 9 (Sept. 2012), 1162fi??1173. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1526-4637.2012.01450.x>
- [7] C. M. Jones, J. Logan, M. Gladden, and M.K. Bohm. 2015. Vital Signs: Demographic and Substance Use Trends Among Heroin Users. *MMWR Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report* 64, 26 (July 2015), 719fi??725. <http://europepmc.org/articles/pmc4584844> Published online.
- [8] Rose A. Judd, Noah Aleshire, Jon E. Zibbell, and R. Matthew Gladden. 2016. *Increases in Drug and Opioid Overdose Deaths, United States, 2000-2014*. techreport 64(50). Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, GA. <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview/mmwrhtml/mmm6450a3.htm> Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (MMWR).
- [9] Wes McKinney. 2017. *Python for Data Analysis*. O'Reilly Media Inc., Sebastopol, CA. <https://github.com/wesm/pydata-book>
- [10] National Institute on Drug Abuse. 2018. Opioid Overdose Crisis. online. (Jan. 2018). <https://www.drugabuse.gov/drugs-abuse/opioids/opioid-overdose-crisis>
- [11] National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA). 2017. *Overdose Death Rates*. Summary. National Institutes of Health (NIH), Washington D.C. <https://www.drugabuse.gov/related-topics/trends-statistics/overdose-death-rates>
- [12] L.M. Reifler, D. Danna Droz, Bailey JE, S.H. Schnoll, R. Fant, R.C. Dart, and B.B. Bartelson. [n. d.]. ([n. d.]).
- [13] McCabe SE, West BT, Teter CJ, and Boyd CJ. 2012. Medical and Nonmedical Use of Prescription Opioids Among High School Seniors in the United States. *Archive of Pediatric Adolescent Medicine* 166, 9 (2012), 797fi??802. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1001/archpediatrics.2012.85>
- [14] Yavin Shaham, Uri Shalev, Lin Lu, Harriet de Wit, and Jane Stewart. 2003. The reinstatement model of drug relapse: history, methodology and major findings. *Psychopharmacology* 168, 1 (01 Jul 2003), 3-20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-002-1224-x>
- [15] Sean M. Shiverick. 2018. Project data codebook for prescription opioid misuse dataset from NSDUH 2015-2016. Google.doc. (March 2018). <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BbMR4-WAm9Ya2ot3A3fteK1Ra71fZjxZjrj6qdRETaQ/edit?usp=sharing>
- [16] G.J. Unick, D. Rosenblum, S. Mars, and D. Ciccarone. 2013. Intertwined Epidemics: National Demographic Trends in Hospitalizations for Heroin- and Opioid-Related Overdoses, 1993fi??2009. *PLoS ONE* 8, 2 (2013), e54496. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0054496>
- [17] Kevin E. Vowles, Mindy L. McEntee, Peter Siyahhana Julnes, Tessaa Frohe, John P. Ney, and David N. van der Goes. 2015. Rates of opioid misuse, abuse, and addiction in chronic pain: a systematic review and data synthesis. *PAIN* 156, 4 (April 2015), 569fi??576. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.j.pain.0000460357.01998.f1>

- [18] M. A. Yokell, N. D. Zaller, M. K. Delgado, N. E. Wang, S. K.McGowan, and T.C. Green. 2013. Clinical and Demographic Characteristics Associated With Opioid Overdose Visits to United States Emergency Departments. In *Proceedings of the American College of Emergency Physicians Annual Meeting*, American College of Emergency Physicians annual meeting (Ed.), Vol. 193. Seattle, WA. <http://www.psychiatristtimes.com/acep2013/opioid-overdose-new-demographic-data-reveal-related-comorbidities>
- [19] Barbara Zedler, Lin Xie, Li Wang, Andrew Joyce, Catherine Vick, Furaha Kariburyo, Pradeep Rajan, Onur Baser, and Lenn Murrelle. 2014. Risk Factors for Serious Prescription Opioid-Related Toxicity or Overdose among Veterans Health Administration Patients. *Pain Medicine* 15, 11 (2014), 1911-1929. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pme.12480>

A TECHNICAL APPENDIX

Note: Tests of the OLS assumptions reported below were conducted using a data subset with additional outliers removed, and therefore the sample N 's reported in this section are different from the sample sizes reported in the body of the paper.

A.1 Detection and Correction of Heteroscedasticity

There was some concern for heteroscedasticity in the data because of the demographic variables measured in cross-section, high degree of skew in the aggregated variables, presence of outliers, and non-normal distributions of errors. An auxiliary regression conducted for the White's test yielded a $R^2 = 0.096$, with $N = 24,963$ and 121 parameters, which provided a $\chi^2 = 2401.44$, that was greater than the critical value of $\chi^2 = 124.34$ ($df=100$), at the $\alpha = 0.05$; the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating evidence of strong heteroscedasticity in the data.

The Goldfield-Quandt Test was conducted using $C = 2952$ (16 parameters), which resulted in a significant F-test result of 1.24 which was greater than the critical value of $F(500,200) = 1.22$, at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level; the null hypothesis was rejected providing evidence of heteroscedasticity. To correct for heteroscedasticity, the Weighted Least Squares (WLS) transformation was used based on the assumption that $\alpha^2 = \alpha^2((AGECAT)^2)$, with PROC MODEL in SAS to obtain the WLS regression equation and White's test for this new model. The White's test from PROC MODEL WLS regression corrected for heteroscedasticity yielded a $\chi^2 = 2081$, $p < 0.0001$, which indicated that heteroscedasticity was reduced but not eliminated from the data.

The same procedure was conducted with the MUPO subset. The auxiliary regression for the White's test yielded an $R^2 = 0.064$ ($N = 6478$, 121 parameters), which provided a $\chi^2 = 414.59$, that was greater than the critical value of $\chi^2 = 124.34$ ($df=100$), at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level; the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating evidence of heteroscedasticity. The Goldfield-Quandt Test was conducted using $C = 1505$ (16 parameters), which resulted in a $F = 1.10$, which was less than the critical value of $F(500,200) = 1.22$, at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level; this non-significant result suggested there was not sufficient evidence of heteroscedasticity. However, the WLS transformations was used based on the assumption that Age Category was contributing to heteroscedasticity in the data.